

AREAS OF CONFLICT BETWEEN PAKISTAN AND AFGHANISTAN (2021-2024): AN ANALYSIS

Abdullah Khan^{*1}, Syed Jamal Hussain Shah², Dr. Muhammad Tariq³^{*1,2}M.Phil. Scholar, Department of Political Science, Hazara University, Mansehra, Pakistan³Lecturer, Department of Political Science, Hazara University, Mansehra, Pakistan¹akhankhan1353@gmail.com, ²gmsshah748@gmail.com, ³muhammadtariq@hu.edu.pkDOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20715917>**Keywords**

Conflict, Border, Pak-Afghan, Trade, Relations

Article History

Received: 29 January 2026

Accepted: 14 March 2026

Published: 28 March 2026

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *
Abdullah Khan**Abstract**

Pak-Afghan relations have passed through many ups and downs during the political history of the two countries. The issue of the validity of the Pak-Afghan border has been of utmost importance due to its historical importance and divergent views by the two states. The end of the twenty years long war in Afghanistan in August 2021 provided the Taliban with the opportunity to retake power in the country. Lack of mutual trust between Pakistan and Afghanistan and the repatriation of the Afghan refugees resulted in the closure of the Pak-Afghan border catering for open conflict. This study aims at analyzing the areas of conflict between the two countries while focusing on the Pak-Afghan trade, issues of Afghan refugees' return to their country and the resultant closure of the Pak-Afghan border. Main findings of the study include the discontinuation of the Pak-Afghan trade along the border, the era of direct confrontation between the two states and the quest for regional peace and stability.

Institute for Excellence in Education & Research

Introduction

Relations between Pakistan and Afghanistan have remained tense due to the issue of infiltration on the Pak-Afghan border. The 9/11 episode of 2001 brought about havoc along the border on both sides as sovereignty of the two countries were put at stake. The prolonged border between the said countries has a significant impact on the relations of the countries. The repatriation of the Afghan refugees who migrated to Pakistan as a result of the Soviet Union intervention in Afghanistan in 1979 has created great tension in the relations of the two states. At the time of the war, the government of Pakistan has to provide all possible support to the Afghan brethren in the hour of need, resulting in the victory of the Afghan government. The end of the Soviet war created greater power vacuum, leadership crisis, and lack of democratic values in Afghanistan. The crisis was followed by the birth of Taliban in Afghan in 1996 who ruled the country till 2001.

The era of Afghan Taliban in Afghanistan came to end in September 2001 in the aftermath of the 9/11 episode.

The US and the allied partners had to fight the war against terrorism in Afghanistan for almost twenty years that again came to end with the rebirth of the Taliban in Afghanistan in August 2021 who took the reign of the country in August 2021. The Russian intervention had compelled the Afghani people to migrate to Pakistan during 1979 and had to stay in Pakistan till the government of Pakistan took stringent measures and asking the Afghan refugees to return to their country. The government of Pakistan, in order to implement the initiative, had to de-notify the 28 Afghan Refugees Camps in the province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa by bringing to an end the 46-years old story of the Afghan refugees (Dawn, Curtains for Afghan refugee camps in KP as Centre de-notifies last 28, 2025). The de-notified camps are situated in different parts of the

country out of which eight are located in the Peshawar, five in Hangu, four in Kohat, three each in Nowshera and Dir, two each in Mardan and Swabi and one in Buner (Dawn, 2025). The notification has also clarified that the property and non-movable assets as mentioned in the de-notified areas would be handed over to the Commissioner of Afghan Refugees. An official of the Afghan Refugees Commissioner states that the number of Afghan camps in the province is 43 out of which five were de-notified in September 2025, ten were de-notified on October 13, 2025 and the remaining 28 on October 15, 2025 (Tariq, Sarwar, & Ali, 2026).

Withdrawal of US Troops and Taliban's

Takeover

The US withdrawal from Afghanistan influenced Pak-Afghan relations. In August 2021, when the US troops left Afghanistan and the democratic government was weakened and failed to operate, the Taliban emerged as rising force in the country by first taking control of Kabul and then took control of the entire country. The move proved to be a great surprise to the regional and the international community with the rebirth of Taliban after almost fighting for twenty years against the US forces. The attitude towards each other changed and the relations between the Afghan Taliban and Pakistan did not show any sign of positive development. It's a worthy happening that when elections are contested in any of the country parties inside countries promotes their agenda and get the response in winning or losing. After winning and losing the previous whole track changes its direction in the country. The foreign policy, leadership relations, charismatic following, national ties and inner governmental machinery are the factors to be molded by the newcomers. But in case of takeover of any of the un-recognized group like Afghan Taliban the situation differs. The charismatic leaders are the one who are not blamed by their follower, what they are doing is no matter. Their right and wrong, favor of the citizens or against have no meaning, their leader is the one who yells the same which is opted by the followers.

The Issue of Pak-Afghan border and Trade

The Pak-Afghan border has been a source of trade and business activities between the two countries since long as the people living across both sides of the border remain dependent on it. The Pashtun tribes, who share common culture, common traditions and have entered into blood relations and have been engaged in joint business enterprises mostly rely on the border for trade and survival. Pakistan has been providing easiest accessibility of routes to Afghanistan for the supply of goods and services due to the long border besides many passes- routes through mountains used for the easy access of people and imports-exports possible through mountain passes. The landlocked nature of Afghanistan makes it more dependent on Pakistan for all business activities.

The repatriation of the Afghan refugees to their parent country by the government of Pakistan resulted in the closure of the border for trade, inflow of the people and business enterprises. The closure of Pak-Afghan border would delimit the trade facilities of the two countries but the former would not suffer to the extent to which the latter is supposed to suffer. In order to minimize dependence on the trade across the border, Afghanistan showed her desire to seek for alternate routes and venues to carry on trade facilities but it would not be able to provide those opportunities to its exporters in the short-to-medium term trade facilities (Rana , 2025). The Iranian routes are longer in distances and more expensive, resulting in higher transaction and fuel costs as compared to Pakistani routes. For example, the areas of Kandahar and Helmand are about 150-300 Kilometer from the Pakistani Chaman-Spin Boldak border but 1,200-1,300 Kilometer to Iran's Zaranj or Delaram borders (Rana , 2025). Similarly, Balkh and Baghlan are roughly 500-700 Kilometer from Pakistan's Torkham-Jalalabad borders and 900-1,000 Kilometer from Iran's Islam Qala (Rana , 2025). The use of alternative routes would result in the increased transport charges, ranging from 30-50%. In all cases, whether the closure of the border or the use of alternate routes would result in creating problems for the farmers and business

communities of the two countries (Tariq, Sarwar, & Ali, 2026).

Major Trade-routes between Pakistan and Afghanistan

Trade between Pakistan and Afghanistan has provided the two states the opportunities to bring them closer to each other and provide business opportunities to the people across both sides of the border. Trade and business activities suffered a setback between the two states when the Pak-Afghan border was closed during mid-October 2025 as a result of the ongoing fighting between the forces of the two states. The stuck of vehicles has also led to the damaging of goods and materials kept in the vehicles and the containers. Both Pakistan and Afghanistan have maintained a significant trade relationship over the past years (Shakoor, 2025). The former exports food products, cement, pharmaceuticals, textiles, and manufactured goods to Afghanistan while the latter exports fresh and dried fruits, vegetables, and minerals to Pakistan (Shakoor, 2025). Thus, the import-export and business between the two states has faced stagnation from the hands of the business community and the business enterprises that remain dependent on trade and business through the border routes (Tariq, Hameedullah, & Hussain, 2026). The trade and business between the two states has been adopted by the people as a source of income and earning a fair bread while any ban in the form of border-closure or restrictions by the concerned authorities or temporary suspension of trade cause huge loss to the people dependent on it.

Improvement in trade was seen between the two countries during July 2020 to June 2024 when Pakistan's imports to Afghanistan witnessed a strong upward trend over the five-year period from 2020 to 2024 with a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 7.55% (Shakoor, 2025). In 2020, Pakistan exported goods worth \$852.31 million, which steadily increased to \$1,140.17 million in 2024. The highest export value was recorded in 2024, while the lowest was in 2022, when exports fell to \$805.14 million (Shakoor, 2025). After this decline in 2022, exports have recovered and have been and have been showing

a growth. Pakistan's imports from Afghanistan, on the other hand, have seen more fluctuations during the stated period. Both imports and exports have faced fluctuations during the period from July 2020 to June 2024. Imports rose from \$468.34 million in 2020 to a peak of \$880.07 million in 2023 (Shakoor, 2025). However, in 2024, imports decreased sharply to \$566.44 million. Despite this volatility, the overall import trend showed moderate growth, with a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 4.87% over the 5-year period (Shakoor, 2025). There have been ups and downs in the trade between Pakistan and Afghanistan during the stated period (Tariq, Hameedullah, & Hussain, 2026).

A Window of Opportunity

The closure of Pak-Afghan border as a result of skirmishes between Afghanistan and Pakistan, the former will have more space for entering into trade and business enterprises with the Central Asian Republics. Bilateral relations are developing to a great extent since the Central Asian States share the goals of increasing trade with Afghanistan and opening up routes through that country connecting them to Pakistani ports on the Arabian Sea (Pannier, 2026). Northern neighbors of Afghanistan are also aware that peace, stability and security in Afghanistan are very important for the regional dynamics of the Central Asian States. Since the independence of the five Central Asian States in 1991, they have been contending with instability and uncertainty along the southern border.

Long history of war, political instability and security concerns in Afghanistan has hampered Afghanistan's capacity to serve as a transit center for trade and emergency; yet there are opportunities to leverage its position for strengthening economic relations between Pakistan and Central Asian States (Wareen, 2026). Afghanistan's cordial relations with these states would result in enhanced regional collaboration and sustained investment. Historically Afghanistan has served as a crucial link in the ancient Silk Road with the aim of

facilitating trade and business between the East and West (Wareen , 2026). Afghanistan's geographic position puts it a gateway for the resource-rich Central Asian Republics for having access to the global market through Pakistan's warm water ports of Karachi and Gawadar. The Central Asian Economic Cooperation (CAREC) program initiated in 2001 for enhancing regional integration has identified Afghanistan as vital player in integrating the region through economy. The CAREC corridor has been designed to improve trade routes and resultantly boosting economy between the Central Afghanistan, Central Asia and Pakistan (Wareen , 2026).

Some researchers are of the view that Chinese investors and labors operating in Afghanistan and who are associated with the mineral extradition projects near Afghanistan-Tajikistan border are faced with persistent threats from militant groups (Dr, 2026). During the period of September 2024 and early 2026, at least seven attacks were recorded in the border regions, resulting in the death of nine Chinese national and injuries to ten others (Dr, 2026). But security incidents may not hinder the trade and business enterprises between the investors as China has emerged as one of the few major powers willing to engage itself economically and make investment with Afghanistan under the Taliban Regime. China remains more concerned with making investment in Afghanistan and particularly her involvement in mining, gold and strategic minerals make China a potential economic partner for Kabul's current government. In the absence of broad international recognition and amid ongoing sanctions, foreign investment from Beijing is widely viewed as critical to stabilizing Afghanistan's fragile economy (Dr, 2026).

Despite efforts for the trade and business activities economic engagement and bilateral trade cannot flourish in an environment stuck by insecurity and instability. The nature of borders, particularly remoteness and mountainous area coupled with treacherous nature of border where many mineral projects are located are prone to armed groups and the militants operating beyond the effective state control (Dr, 2026). In the wake

of security challenges, urban centers may appear stable but peripheral regions may often present governance and enforcement challenges. The gap between urban and peripheral regions creates a dual burden for the Taliban Regime; projecting an image of national stability while confronting decentralized militant threats undermining that narrative (Dr, 2026). Afghanistan is very important to the regional dynamics since it lies at the crossroads of South and Central Asia, linking regional trade corridors and energy routes. The regional powers look at a very stable and protected Afghanistan particularly China where she considers stability in Afghanistan intersects with concerns about cross- border militancy and the protection of Belt and Road-linked interests (Dr, 2026).

Challenges before the Taliban Government

Soon after the takeover of the country by the Afghan Taliban in August 2021 as a result of the US withdrawal from Afghanistan, the Taliban established their government in the country o the utter exclusion of other stakeholders in the country. But it is also a fact that the during the US operations in Afghanistan, when the country was ruled by democratic regimes, the Taliban were also excluded from the mainstream politics of the country. The drawdown of the US forces from Afghanistan that started in 2014 encompassing different phases for the withdrawal of the NATO forces from Afghanistan led to the rebirth of the government of the Afghan Taliban in Afghanistan. The drawdown scenario of the NATO forces, if on one hand provided the opportunity of the withdrawal of the foreign troops from Afghanistan but on the other hand, faced the country with certain severe challenges and issues leading towards the weakness and fragility of the government. Some of these challenges include the severe economic downturn adding further to the vulnerability of population in a dilemma. Coupled with these are the challenges of the accommodation of the refugees that had to be adjusted after repatriation from both Pakistan and the Iran, the issues of poverty, hunger, unemployment and the natural disasters in the form of food insecurity, COVID-19, and

earthquakes. In order to tackle the issues, the government of Taliban needs to focus on the collective efforts by the various stakeholders and help the needy people irrespective of religion, caste, creed, language, race and culture (CRISIS, 2021)

The strategy of the government of Pakistan for the repatriation of the Afghan refugees is an important step towards lessening the burden on the exchequer of the government and proper use of the resources of the country by the people of Pakistan. In continuation of the Afghan refugees repatriation move, the government of Pakistan has been making all possible arrangements for sending them back to their country. Since late 2023, more than 665,000 Afghan refugees have been forced back to their country as part of the campaign (Hassan, 2025). Many of these refugees have been living in Pakistan for decades or have been born here (Tariq & Hameed , Instability in Afghanistan: Economic Contraction and Humanitarian Crisis, 2025). It is important to note that three generations of the Afghan refugees have been residing over here and are not ready to leave Pakistan. Those who have reached their parent country have been faced with severe problems of finances, lack of housing facilities and access to the schools and education facilities (Tariq, Ikramullah , & Gul, 2025).

The unwillingness of the Afghan refugees to return to their country has been viewed with great concern by the government of Pakistan since the Afghan refugees have spent more than four decades and now the people of Afghanistan are having government of their own. The repatriation move of the Afghan refugees were further given impetus by the de-notification of Afghan Refugee Camps by the government of Pakistan whereby 28 Afghan Refugee Camps were de-notified in the province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa bringing to an end the 46- years old history of the Afghan refugees in Pakistan (Dawn, Curtains for Afghan refugee camps in KP as Centre de-notifies last 28, 2025). The de-notified camps are situated in different parts of the country out of which eight are located in the Peshawar, five in Hangu, four in Kohat, three each in Nowshera and Dir, two each in Mardan

and Swabi and one in Buner (Dawn, Curtains for Afghan refugee camps in KP as Centre de-notifies last 28, 2025). The notification has also clarified that the property and non-movable assets as mentioned in the de-notified areas would be handed over to the Commissioner of Afghan Refugees. An official of the Afghan Refugees Commissioner states that the number of Afghan camps in the province is 43 out of which five were de-notified in September 2025, ten were de-notified on October 13, 2025 and the remaining 28 on October 15, 2025 (Tariq & Hameed , Instability in Afghanistan: Economic Contraction and Humanitarian Crisis, 2025).

The de-notification of the Afghan Refugees Camps aims at sending back approximately 350, 000 Afghan Refugees to their parent country. According to a report of the International Organization for Migration states that Pakistan has been able in returning 702, 643 refugees to Afghanistan since April 2025 while 90, 302 of them have been deported. A comparative analysis of the repatriation and deportations shows that a decrease of 28% has been noted in the former while an increase of 82% has been recorded in the latter. According to the statistics of the government about 1,5 million had returned to Afghanistan since September 15, 2023 while 750, 685 had reached the country since January 1, 2025. In the current scenario, even the Taliban regime is not in favor of Pakistan and the Taliban are hurting the interest of Pakistan by opening up to India (Katju, 2025). The repatriation move has been facing certain problems partly because the refugees are not willing to return to their country after spending almost 46 years in Pakistan and partly due to problems faced by the parent country for making proper arrangement and their accommodation facilities (Tariq & Hameed , Instability in Afghanistan: Economic Contraction and Humanitarian Crisis, 2025).

Tremendous increase in arrest and detention of the Afghan refugees marked January 2026 touching almost 18% as compared to the report of a week ago (period between January 1, 2026 to January 10, 2026) meaning thereby a very rapid increase during the beginning of 2026 (Ahmed K. , 2026). Three main areas of concern during the

period included Chaghi, Pishin and Islamabad (Ahmed K. , 2026). The UN Refugee Agency, the UNHCR, and the UN Migration Office, IOM opine that during January 4 to January 10, 2026, of the total reported arrests and detentions about 73% came from Balochistan while 16% came from Islamabad. Moreover, of all the arrested and detained people during the period, Afghan Citizen Card holders and undocumented Afghan represented 87% of the total arrest and detentions while the number of Proof Registration holders stood a 13% (Tariq , Raza, & Raja , The Issue of Pak-Afghan Border Closure: Implications for Stakeholders, 2026). According to the data released by UNHCR and IOM showing that a total of 130, 999 Afghan Nationals were arrested during September 15, 2025 to January 10, 2026 (Ahmed K. , 2026). Of these arrests, most of these were made in Balochistan amounting to 68%, followed by Islamabad amounting to 19%, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa 6%, Punjab 4% and Sindh 3% (Ahmed K. , 2026).

Conclusion

Pak-Afghan relations entered a new phase of embryonic stage in the August 2021 scenario with the re-emergence of the Taliban. With the rebirth of Taliban, the regional and world community had to focus their eyes on the new governance of the Taliban government in Afghanistan. Soon after the takeover, the Taliban had to reconsider foreign policy and focused on their relations with the regional dynamics. In their previous regime during 1996-2001, the Taliban had to maintain good relations with the neighboring country of Pakistan because the government of Taliban was supported by either Pakistan or the Taliban were pleased with the role of Pakistan during the Russian intervention in Afghanistan. The current Taliban regime is more interested in strengthening relations with the neighboring countries and particularly India for their diverging views with the Pakistani government on many areas pertaining to their respective national interest.

Trade relations also worsened between the two countries due to the issue of the repatriation of

the Afghan refugees to Afghanistan, very much against the interest of the Afghan refugees. The government of Pakistan, in order to provide relief to their nationals and lessen the burden on the resources of the country had to reiterate the return of Afghan refugees to their parent country, which the refugees did not like and showed their unwillingness to comply with the decision. The de-notification of the Afghan refugees' camps by the government of Pakistan had to bring the two countries in open confrontations against each other causing irreparable loss to the business and trade community of the two countries and particularly those were dependent on the bilateral trade for many years. The worst scenario came when the Pak-Afghan border was closed by the government of Pakistan in the wake of conflict and open confrontations between the law enforcement agencies of the two countries.

References

- AFGHANISTAN'S HUMANITARIAN CRISIS. (2021). Retrieved from <https://issi.org.pk/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/Report-ISSI-KIP.pdf> The Centre for Afghanistan, Middle East & Africa (CAMEA), Institute of Strategic Studies Islamabad (ISSI) & The Kabul Institute for Peace (KIP)
- Ahmed, K. (2026, January 17). Arrest, Detention of Afghan Increased in 18pc In Jan: UN-IOM. Dawn Newspaper. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1967425/arrest-detention-of-afghans-increased-18pc-in-jan-un-iom>.
- Dawn. (2025, October 16). Curtains for Afghan refugee camps in KP as Centre de-notifies last 28. Rawalpindi , Punjab, Pakistan : <https://www.dawn.com/news/1949157/curtains-for-refugee-camps-in-kp-as-centre-de-notifies-last-28>.
- Dr, F. A. (2026, February 24). Afghanistan's Fragile Peace and the Test of Security for Foreign Investment. Minute Mirror. <https://minutemirror.com.pk/afghanistans-fragile-peace-and-the-test-of-security-for-foreign-investment-511021/>.

- Hassan, T. (2025, October 13). Afghanistan Events of 2024 . <https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2025/country-chapters/afghanistan> Afghanistan World Report .
- Katju, V. (2025, October 16). Pakistan-Afghanistan ties: Past imperfect, present tense, future uncertain. <https://indianexpress.com/article/explained/pakistan-afghanistan-ties-past-imperfect-present-tense-future-uncertain-10309506/>.
- Pannier, B. (2026, February 20). From Security Threat to Economic Partner: Central Asia's New 'View' of Afghanistan. The Times of Central Asia . <https://timesca.com/from-security-threat-to-economic-partner-central-asias-new-view-of-afghanistan/>.
- Rana , S. (2025, November 16). Why Pakistan's border closure is squeezing Afghanistan's economy. Newspaper, Magazine . <https://tribune.com.pk/story/2577676/fractured-ties>.
- Shakoor, S. S. (2025). Pakistan-Afghanistan Bilateral Trade & Afghanistan Trade with other Regional Countries . Pakistan Buisness Council .
- Tariq , D. M., & Hameed , M. (2025, 11 7). Instability in Afghanistan: Economic Contraction and Humanitarian Crisis. PakistanJournalofSocialSciencesReview(PJSSR), 4(6), 173-181 ISSN(e)2959-8052.
- Tariq , D. M., Raza, S., & Raja , I. (2026, February 9). The Issue of Pak-Afghan Border Closure: Implications for Stakeholders. Journal of Media Horizon, 7(2), 100-106.
- Tariq, D. M., Ikramullah , & Gul, S. (2025, 11 5). The Issue of Human Rights in Afghanistan: An Appraisal. Vol. 4 No. 6 (2025): Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences Review (PJSSR), 85-93.
- Wareen , G. (2026, February). Afghanistan's Strategic Role in Regional Connectivity: Challenges and Opportunities for Pakistan and Central Asia. Center for Research and Security Studies . <https://crss.pk/afghanistans-strategic-role-in-regional-connectivity-challenges-and-opportunities-for-pakistan-and-central-asia/>.